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Effects of Untreated Sewage on Marine Environment-A Case Study of Karachi

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Received Date: 16-Oct-2020

Accepted Date: 30-Oct-2020

Published Date: 31-Oct-2020

Abstract

The objective of the paper was to identify the impact of untreated municipal sewage on the marine environment along the coast of Karachi. Karachi, the financial capital of Pakistan, is facing a serious sanitation and sewage crisis. About 471 million gallon per day (MGD) of municipal wastewater is discharged into the sea without treatment. It produces over 12,000 tons of solid waste every day and about sixty percent of solid waste is dumped in designated landfills and remaining solid waste remains in the streets and roads. Results concluded that heavy discharge of untreated municipal wastewater into Arabian Sea; deteriorate the coastal areas of Karachi, production of marine fisheries become sluggish, high risk to human health and extinction of four types of mangrove forests. It was observed that the average annual growth rate of marine fish catch remained 0.68 percent during 2000-19 which is a very a nominal growth rate. Whereas, the average annual growth rate of inland fish catch remained 3.55 percent during the same period. The habitat on the Gizri stream, Manora Island, Clifton and Sea view beaches have been deteriorated and most of the territories of these reservoirs are deprived of a congenial environment. Marine life is contaminated with lead and consumption of seafood by people can cause a health hazard for the residents of the city. In order to solve the biggest sewage problem in Karachi, it is recommended that the projects initiated under the Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan be implemented as a priority, and efforts should be made to functionalize all treatment plants at earliest. It is necessary to create an independent high-power committee to monitor the future wastewater flow into the Arabian Sea and hold them responsible for not fulfilling their statutory role in managing the sewage system for the collection, pumping, treatment and disposal of domestic and industrial waste.

Keywords: Extinction, Hazardous, Mangroves, Marine pollution, Municipal sewage, Solid waste

Abbreviation

DHA	Defence Housing Authority
DMC	District Municipal Corporation
GTSs	Garbage Transfer Stations
KCCI	Karachi Chamber of Commerce & Industry
KSDP	Karachi Strategic Development Plan
KMC	Karachi Metropolitan Corporation
KPT	Karachi Port Trust
KWSB	Karachi Water & Sewerage Board
LFSs	Landfill Sites
MFF	Mangroves for the Future
MGD	Million Gallons per Day
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal

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SSWMB Sindh Solid Waste Management Board
STP Sewerage Treatment Plant

1-Introduction

Marine pollution in the Arabian Sea, especially on the Karachi coast, has become a serious danger to the lives of people and marine environment. In Pakistan, there is serious ignorance of marine pollution. The inappropriate disposal of untreated domestic wastewater and industrial effluents into shallow sea water in large coastal dwellings is common practice. It not only destruct the see water quality but also creates harmful impact over marine life particularly along the Karachi coast side. The impurities added in sea water through industrial waste are more harmful than domestic waste. The city of Karachi, with an estimated population of 1.068 million in 1951, 9.856 million in 1998 and reached at 16.053 million in 2017 (**GoP-2017**). **Figure-1** shows an upward trend in the population of city. The number of people may also be more than the official figures due to the huge migration from other parts of the country which also put pressure on the exiting sewerage system of Karachi.

Karachi has the largest industrial installations, where 6 industrial sites accommodate 10,000 industrial units, including 700 tanneries. About 3000 enterprises operate in the industrial zone of Korangi, off the coast of Karachi. The sum of municipal, domestic and industrial waste is around 500 million gallon per day (**World Bank, 2005**). The recycling process of waste is inefficient in Karachi, so waste goes to sea without getting treatment and polluted the marine life there. The disposal of solid waste includes plastic elements beside other impurities, which are very harmful for fish growth than any other waste (**Qureshi, 2005**).

The six district of Karachi produces around 12000 tons of solid waste and it is increasing day by day, 40 percent of said waste remains in streets and roads and remaining 60 percent is dumped in landfills (**Shahid and Nergis, 2014**). The solid that remains in the city can be found in gardens, parks, domestic and commercial trash (**Jilani, 2007**). There are many places in Karachi where waste can be dumped but it over flows shows least capacity and needs more places to allocate to get significant results. Sometimes people dumped their waste on road side, which create problem for municipal employees. Outside garbage burning are observed in various areas and it create environmental problems (**Sabir et al., 2016**).

In Karachi, solid waste management system in to six towns named as West, East, South, Central, Korangi and Malir town. Being a metropolitan city, Karachi is divided in six managerial zones and each zone (District Municipal Corporation) is liable to provide municipal services and to manage the solid waste (**KCCI, 2018**). Sindh Solid Waste Management Board (SSWMB) was established by government of Sindh in 2014 under the Sindh Solid Waste Management Board Act of 2014 (IV of 2014). In accordance of this act, each DMC's is subject to dispose its services for efficient provision of sanitation services, provision pollution free environment in entire province of Sindh. Two DMC's out of six DMC's responsibilities transferred to the Board (**GoS, 2017**). It was decided that board operation will be extended to entire province within five years but board failed to develop Garbage Transfer Stations (GTSs) & Land Fill Sites (LFSs) in Sindh for disposal of solid waste.

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The cantonment area of Karachi including Karachi Port Trust (KPT), Defence Housing Authority (DHA) Karachi has its own solid waste management system which is working efficiently and it is not under the board discipline, working independently. There are two places outside the city which have capacity to accommodate 9,500 tons of waste (**Table-1**). Gondpass and Jam Chakro each area consists of 500 acres, which is located in North West of Karachi. These landfills are insufficient to meet the solid waste demand of the metropolitan city, the demand exists to explore the area of landfills (**KCCI, 2018**).

S. No	Name of Landfill site	Waste handling capacity (tons/day)
1	Jam Chakro, near Surjani Town	Around 8,000 tons
2	Gondpass	Around 1,500 tons
3	Dhabeji (under progress)	Not commissioned

Source: KCCI Research, 2018

Inefficient handling of solid waste management is not only due to lack of but also provision of improper funds. The tools and machinery required are less in numbers, solid bins allocated are insufficient and small in size which does not meet the demand of people of said areas and create trouble for them to dispose their waste and eventually it creates environmental issues for the society. The vehicles that pass the garbage to landfill are insufficient and which are working have depreciated and responsible to pollute the road sides.

In industrial areas of Landhi and Korangi water-borne disease is raising and usually reported in hospitals located nearby of these areas (**Frisbie et al., 2002**). The wastewater from Bin Qasim industrial zone, Korangi, Landhi, Karachi export zone, and Pakistan steel mill is discharged directly into seawater (**Janus & Krajnc, 1990**). The impurities discharged from industrial zones contain around 23 percent of toxic heavy metals such as uranium, tin, Zinc, silver, platinum, nickel, mercury, vanadium, thallium, tellurium, lead, iron, gallium, copper, cobalt, chromium, cerium, cadmium, bismuth, arsenic and antimony (**Khan et al., 2004**). The mangrove forests which provide lives to fisherman, marine lives, protect the lives from ocean disasters are under real threat due to addition of impurities in ocean (**Fawell et al., 1996**). The seafood supply will restrict and will create problems for human lives as well like, anemia, heart attack, kidney failure, and brain damage. The impact of water on seabirds, fish species and humans along with mangroves and proposing control measures may get benefits for society (**Nadeem-ul-Haq et al., 2009**). Such benefits can be managed by avoiding the cost of damage. These benefits consist of reestablishing bearable yields of natural ecosystems such as aquaculture and fisheries, as well as civilizing the environmental values of tourism and entertaining activities (**Naqvi, 2006**).

2- Significance of Karachi

Karachi is back bone of Pakistan in all respects; it is a largest populated city, industrial and financial hub, major contributor in industrial trade and GDP of Pakistan (KSDP-2020, 2007). Around 70% of industrial units are located in Karachi, including electronic goods, oil refineries, tanneries, pharmaceuticals, chemicals, textiles, food, iron and steel and thermal energy production, etc. Wharf Industrial Zone, Landhi Industrial Estate (L.I.T.E), Korangi Industrial zone, and Sindh Industrial Trading Estate (S.I.T.E) contain 6000 industrial units (**MFF Pakistan, 2016**). The industrial and commercial zones of Karachi generate employment opportunities up to 71.6 percent of the total employed labor force in Sindh. The manufacturing units are 71.4 percent of the total manufacturing units in Sindh (**Khuhro, et al., 1997**). The cargo management of export and import at the Karachi port was 2.8 million tons in 1951, 29 million tons in 2001 and 54.685 million tons in 2018 (**Hasan, 2000**). The industrial growth creates some illegal groups that were involved in illegal activities and industry decorates because of all this. In results maximum industrial number of units shifted to Punjab and medium-sized enterprises in Dubai, Malaysia, Sri Lanka and Singapore (due to the safe location and labor laws favorable to employers) which destroy the production hub of Karachi (**Ebrahim, 2012**).

Even then this shock shifting of industrial unit to other location, Karachi still has the significant number of industrial units, international banks, multinational companies are working in Karachi. The Karachi industrial base includes industries in seven main concentrations, namely: North Karachi, Federal 'B' Area, Sindh, Port

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Qasim, Export Processing Zone, Landhi and Korangi Industrial Estates. Karachi is a low cost city, a poor can survive with limited resources. Karachi is a low cost city; labor can get their jobs on daily basis and earns sufficiently to meet their living means. There are many Kachi Abadies in Karachi, where people can live with low cost of living (KSDP-2020, 2007). The treatments facilities which are needed by the industrial units are absent due to lack of funds and very few industrial units have are providing treatment facilities towards society.

3- Problem Statement

Karachi, the financial capital of Pakistan, is facing a serious sanitation and sewage crisis; Unhygienic conditions on the coast, clogged nullahs, blocked drains, and broken main sewer pipes and sewage treatment plants. Karachi produces more than 12,000 tons of solid waste every day in six districts, and about sixty percent of solid waste is dumped in landfills, and the remaining forty percent remains on the streets and roads of the city (Shahid and Nergis, 2014). These solid waste produced in the city include industrial effluents, domestic wastewater, commercial, trash, parks and gardens residuals (Jilani, 2007). There are only two landfills in the city; Gondpass and Jam Chakro, which have a waste storage capacity of just 9,500 tons versus 12,000 tons per day. However, these landfills are located in remote areas of northwest of Karachi, which carriers set aside for daily throughput (KCCI, 2018).

Most of the municipal wastewater and remaining solid waste flows through open nallahs and drains proposed and built to service storm water during rainfall and are discharged into the sea without treatment. There are three Sewerage Treatment Plants (STP) situated at various locations in Karachi, namely STP-I at SITE, STP-II in Mehmoodabad and STP-III in Mauripur. Approximately 471 million gallons per day (MGD) of wastewater is produced in city, but nothing is treated in those sewage treatment plants due to non-functionality of plants for the last many years (KWSB, 2018). Consequently, raw and completely untreated wastewater is discharged into the Arabian Sea. Table-2 shows the number of Treatment Plants and its capacity of treatment, situated in various parts of Karachi.

Particulars	TP-I (SITE)	TP-II (Mehmoodabad)	TP-III (Mauripur)
Drainage Area	F.B. Area, Liaquatabad, Nazimabad & North Nazimabad, part of Orangi town, Pak Colony etc.	Old City Areas, Clifton, Societies, Mehmoodabad, part of Azam Basti, Dada Bhai, Saddar, Malir	Old Lyari, Garden East and West, Gulshan-e-Iqbal, PIB colony, Soldier Bazar, Baldia, Nazimabad, North Karachi
Site Area	120 acres (48.6 ha)	120 acres (48.6 ha)	545 acres (221 ha)
Year of construction	1960/1995 (rehabilitated)	1960/1996 (rehabilitated)	1998
Treatment process	Trickling Filter Process	Trickling Filter Process	Anaerobic + Facultative Pond
Capacity (MGD)	51	46	54
Present Flow Rate (MGD)	Non-functional	Non-functional	Non-functional
Source: KW&SB,2018			

The land allocated by government for the construction of STP-II for treatment / lagoon/ storage of sewage was leased out for residential purpose by KMC, and the other major portion of the land allocated for treatment plant land was illegally encroached by the land mafia. Consequently, without the initial re-ownership of the encroached and / or leased land, this plant cannot be put into operation. Furthermore, serious efforts were not made to functionalize the STP-I and STP-III for the treatment of wastewater. The huge quantity of sewage is being discharged into Sea without treatment in various Treatment Plants due non-functionality. It creates marine pollution as well as environmental degradation in Arabian Sea. Due to ignorance of pollution control authorities, environmental situation is becoming worst day by day and society

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is unable to pay the cost of said environmental deteriorated situation. The costal side is not only under threat but marine lives as well, in results fisher man income is at stake because of said polluted environment.

4- The scope of the current study

The scope of current study is to identify the impact of drain of untreated municipal waste into sea and to pass some suggestion to save the marine life because of this irresponsible action by board authorities.

5- The objective of the current study

This paper is to classify the main impacts of untreated municipal sewage on marine environment and to suggest the policy measure to prevent marine pollution.

6-Analysis & Discussion

6.1- Effects of untreated sewage on marine environment

6.1.1-Sluggish trend in production of marine fisheries: Karachi is the hub of marine fishing industry with about 13,000 fishing vessels and 6,000 of trawlers are being used by Karachi Fish Harbour. About 2,600 shrimp trawlers and 3,600 gill netters made the marine fishing fleet, other fishing boats are primarily outboard motor-sailing boats. Pakistan is rich in both marine and inland fish resources; marine fishing is conducted in the coastal areas of Sindh and Baluchistan, while inland fishing comprise rivers, lakes, canals, reservoirs, dhoras, dhands, village ponds and waterlogged areas(Memon, 2012).

Karachi is one of the most important fishing ports of Pakistan. Pakistan has both a domestic and an international market for fish, shrimps and fish related products. At the local level, catch from marine fisheries is delivered to local fish markets; Processed or frozen fish is available at several large department stores in Karachi.Pakistan has a good international fishing market and exports about 30 to 40 percent of total fish catch to about 30 countries and earn substantial foreign exchange. Marine fishing accounts for about 64 percent of total production, including fish and shrimp. Shrimp, however, make up only 15 percent of the production; nevertheless, they are of great importance mainly because of their value and demand in foreign markets. As for inland fisheries, it accounts for 36 percent of the total production (Memon, 2012).

Table-3 shows that the total fish catch remained 615 thousand tons (28.8 percent inland and 71.2 percent marine fish catch) in 2000 and this trend remained sluggish and total fish catch reached at 799 thousand tons (37.7 percent inland and 62.3 percent marine fish catch) in 2019. This pattern showed the declining share of marine fish catchment in total fish production. The average annual growth rate of marine fish catch remained 0.68 percent during 2000-19 which was very nominal growth, on the other side, the average annual growth rate of inland fish catch remained 3.55 percent in the same period, which was more significant than the marine fish production.

Year	Inland	Marine	Total
2000	176	438	615
2001	179	451	630
2002	175	480	655
2003	161	401	562
2004	166	401	566
2005	186	387	573
2006	225	349	574
2007	230	343	573
2008	236	345	580
2009	225	425	650
2010	240	430	670
2011	250	450	700

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2012	260	465	725
2013	262	467	729
2014	265	470	735
2015	285	480	765
2016	295	493	788
2017	298	498	796
2018	304	502	806
2019	301	498	799
Source: Marine Fisheries Department, Government of Pakistan, 2020			

The serious environmental consequences are subject to pollutants of mangrove area, for example toxic pollutants are threat for spawning grounds for fishes and its commercialization in the market. The Malir and Lyari Rivers bring untreated sewage of domestic and industrial origin from the numerous sites of Karachi (Shahzad et al., 2009).

Pakistan has a small fishing industry that makes a significant contribution to the economy. But the poisonous waters of our coast destroy this industry, as the toxins absorbed by the fish enter the food chain, causing health problems and from time to time refusing to export our fish to foreign importers. Due to ecosystem degradation, unsustainable exploitation of marine resources, some fish species either disappeared or their production was slow down (Rafique & Shah, 2019). It was observed that marine fish was declined in coastal areas due to discharged of municipal water. The fishermen preferred to catch fish from deep sea which increased human efforts as well as the consumption of more fuel used during the fishing activities. Figure-2 shows some upward trend of marine catch during 2000 to 2002 and then started to decline till 2014 to reach at previous maximum output. The trend of marine catch has shown sluggish trend from 2015, despite the fishing from deep Sea of Karachi coast and some other coastal areas of Baluchistan.

Source: Marine Fisheries Department, Government of Pakistan, 2020

A large load of water pollution disrupted fishing activities, paralyzed economic growth and development, and severely damaged local fishing communities, depriving them of the livelihoods of their ancestors. Unfortunately, our civil society, especially the public, private sector, the media and the state, neglected this problem and ultimately drew attention to this worsening situation, ultimately wastewater in is growing, and the situation is frightening. It is a threat to life, livelihoods and the natural environment and resources (Frauchiger et al., 2004). The environmental deterioration is a cause to diminish natural wealth and enhances some social threats like poverty, hunger, unemployment and crime. Public pressure groups must highlight this issue to save the social and economic life of the society (Ahmad et al., 2004).

6.1.2- Deterioration in coastal areas of Karachi

Municipal wastewater and remaining residuals of solid waste more than 471 million gallons per day (MGD) pass through various drains, nullahs and two major rivers such as Malir and Lyari and finally discharged into Arabian Sea without treatment (KWSB, 2018). Municipal wastewater includes industrial as well as domestic

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wastewater; it also contains storm water runoff. Industrial wastewater contains a wide range of chemicals, including chemicals, acids, radioactive, salts and petrochemicals. Drugs and its other residuals also intensify the marine pollution. Domestic wastewater holds contaminants from biohazard and micro-plastic particles to soap and fats. The other major contributor is agricultural wastewater; which includes fertilizers, pesticides, salts and other bio-hazards. Storm drains transport pollutants from enclosures and parks as well as from streets and parking lots (Blaettler, 2018). Due to industrial and household untreated discharge of sewage water into Sea, Coastal areas of the city become polluted and are at verge of destruction. Marine life is contaminated with lead. Human consumption of such seafood can cause Kidney failure, brain damage and anaemia (KSDP-2020, 2007). The release of other chemicals in the marine environment causes a decrease in oxygen levels, deterioration in plant life, and a serious reduction in sea water quality. As a result, all levels of marine life are deteriorated and animals, marine fisheries and plants are severely affected (Vikas et al., 2015).

A huge quantity of wastewater is being discharged into Sea, the habitat on the Gizri stream, Manora Island, Clifton and Sea view beaches has been deteriorated, and most of the territories of these reservoirs are deprived of a congenial environment. In addition, most of the Creek system adjacent to the Port Qasim is heavily polluted due to thermal discharges from power plants, heavy metals from a Steel Mill and tanneries, as well as discharges of organic matter from a cattle colony. The solid waste which is dumped on coastal area polluted the shallow coastal water and created a real threat to marine lives such as jellyfish, sea turtles, who try to absorb plastic bags, considering them their favorite food (MFF Pakistan, 2016).

6.1.3- Human Health Hazards

Karachi residents are even more punished by dumping untreated sewers into the Arabian Sea, which pollutes the beaches and coast and creates another health hazard. People are also unable to use the city beaches for recreation and relaxation. Monitoring of water quality on the beach is not carried out; however, since untreated sewage is discharged into the sea, the danger of swimming or wading through such water is assorted. The beaches are also littered with hazardous waste that tides lay on the beach, such as discarded injection needles. Rivers and other water channels in Karachi have also become open sewer waters. If the situation is not resolved immediately, this can lead to an epidemic of infectious diseases. Biological risks found in sewage water include fungi, parasites, viruses and bacteria. This biological waste from houses, parks, farms, industries and beaches causes various health issues for human as well as marine life. Consequently, it affects beauty of beaches, fish hatcheries, exports of fish related products, tourism industry and further deteriorates aquatic environment.

6.1.4- Destruction of Mangrove Forests

Mangroves are important for the environment, ecology and livelihoods of communities that depend on the resources produced and supported by these key ecosystems. They are known as places with high biological productivity and as natural nurseries for various marine organisms. Mangroves reduce marine erosion by delaying sediment, stabilizing the coastal zone and thereby protecting the coast from storm surges and cyclones. In addition, it is providing marine fish as well as other resources (such as firewood) to people living near mangroves. Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 14 focuses on fisheries, one of the ecosystem services provided by mangroves, and many coastal communities in the tropics directly use mangroves as fishing grounds and nurseries. The complex root systems of mangroves protect young fish from predators and provide them with food and nutrients. Mangroves provide complementary ecosystem services to coastal communities, including storm protection, pollution traps, and various cultural ecosystem services. Mangroves have recently been high on the political agenda of many international organizations due to their role in carbon sequestration and storage (Friess et al., 2019).

Mangroves in Pakistan are very common in the Indus Delta, which accounts for 97 percent of the total coverage of mangroves; whereas other 3 percent of mangroves exist at coastal site of Miani-Hor, Kalamat-Hor, Jiwani and Baluchistan. The Indus Delta contains eight species of mangroves; four of them became extinct due to increased salinity due to untreated municipal waste and other pollutants (table-4). *Avicennia*

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marina is main specie that is around 90 percent of all mangrove species found in Pakistan. Other species include *Aegiceras corniculatum*, *Ceriops tagal*, and *Rhizophora mucronata*.

S. No	Mangrove Species	Status
1	<i>Avicennia marina</i>	Present
2	<i>Rhizophora mucronata</i>	Present
3	<i>Ceriops tagal</i>	Present
4	<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i>	Present
5	<i>Ceriops roxburgiana</i>	Extinct
6	<i>Bruguiera congugata</i>	Extinct
7	<i>Rhizophora apiculata</i>	Extinct
8	<i>Sonneratia caseolaris</i>	Extinct

Source: MFF Pakistan, 2016

In Baluchistan, three main types of mangroves are found along the coast of Makran. Miani Hor is the only area where three species of mangroves are found, including *Ceriops tagal*, *Rhizophora mucronata*. *Avicennia marina* is the only species of mangroves that are found in the bay of Kalmat Hor (Pasni) and Gawatar (Jiwani) [MFF Pakistan, 2016]. The polluted seawater from the city of Karachi is transported eastward by summer currents to the mangroves of the Indus Delta. Karachi is located near the Indus delta, and most of the streams located in the southeast of the city of Karachi play a vital role in its contamination. Mangroves are known for their importance to minimize the impact of sea water in the delta areas. But due to the constant and huge discharge of chemicals and sewage, the mangroves were destroyed (Rafique & Shah, 2019).

Mangroves play the role of nurseries for marine fishing due to its complex root system. It protects juvenile fish from predators, and also provides them with food and nutrients. Due to the huge discharge of municipal waste into the sea, these marine fish hatcheries have virtually disappeared, resulting in a reduction in marine fisheries and huge pollution of coastal areas.

7-Remedial measures to prevent marine pollution

The Karachi Water & Sewerage Board (KWSB) designed by government of Sindh under the act which is passed in 1996 by Sindh provincial assembly. The basic objective of said board was to fulfill the demand of domestic and industrial water uses and distribution of drinkable water to Karachi residents (GoS, 1996). Study shows that huge untreated sewage about 471 MGD is being discharged into the sea, resultantly, the coast of Karachi has become highly polluted, production of marine fisheries becomes sluggish, mangroves are depleting quickly and there is a great danger to human health. While addressing the biggest problem of Karachi, the Government of Sindh with the assistance of federal government initiated S-III project i.e. Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan (S-III) with Rs 7.982 billion on costs sharing of 50:50 bases during, 2007. The project was initiated without the preparation of feasibility study as required under the law and few additional works were incorporated in the initial PC-I and was revised upto Rs 36.117 billion during, 2018 (KWSB, 2018).

The project accommodates the spread of wastewater in the Lyari and Malir river basins through the RCC alternative channel and their sewage treatment plants until their final discharge into the sea. Revised PC-I of the Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan S-III Project work was to be approved for in the Malir and Lyari river basins along with the development and building of treatment services. It was planned to build five contract packages with a total length of 22.74 kilometers along with the Malir trunk sewer and eight contract packages with a total length of 33.32 kilometers along with the Lyari trunk sewer. Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan (S-III Project) was initiated to improve the environmental and sanitation conditions of the Karachi through a well integrated system of collection, treatment and disposal of sewage into sea. The other objectives were to improve environmental condition at coastal areas & beaches, maintain marine ecological balance, production of healthy sea food in place of existing hazardous sea food production around Karachi, increase fishery export and save the citizens from health hazards (KWSB, 2018).

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The existing sewage treatment capacity at three treatment facilities located in the city was 151 MGD, but all of them did not work. The KW&SB planned to enhance the capacity of the sewerage Treatment capacity of Plants upto 460 MGD through the execution of Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan S-III Project (KWSB, 2018). The Karachi Port Trust (KPT) and the Sindh government agreed on the possession of 150 acres of land for the construction of a Sewage Treatment Plant-V in Mai Kolachi in the larger public interest. The scheme consisted of sewage treatment plant with a capacity of 100 MGD i.e. 60 MGD at stage-I and 40 MGD at stage-II (KPT-2018).

Table-5 shows the status of the works awarded and the physical completion of the treatment facilities during the study period. This showed that TP-I work was 55 percent completed in rehabilitation and 12 percent was completed in expansion. Similarly, Treatment Plant-III work was 95 percent in rehabilitation and only 8 percent was completed in expansion. The land allocated for TP-II was illegally encroached by land mafia and board was unable to vacate the same land for the construction of treatment plant. The work on TP-IV and TP-V was not initiated by the executing agencies, which showed non-seriousness of government bodies regarding the problems of city residents.

S. No	Sewage Treatment Plant	Stage	Contract cost million Rs.	Phases	Proposed Treatment Capacity	Physical Progress in percent
1	Treatment Plant-I, at Haroonabad S.I.T.E (Pak Oasis)	Stage-I	2,487	Rehabilitation	100	55
		Stage-II	1,403	Expansion		12
2	Treatment Plant-II at Mehmoodabad		0	Land encroached	Nil	0
3	Treatment Plant-III at Mauripur (Pak Oasis)	Stage-I	1,513	Rehabilitation	180	95
		Stage-II	6,386	Expansion		8
4	Treatment Plant-IV at Korangi	Initial	0	TP-IV & V works are not initiated	180	0
5	Treatment Plant-V at Mai Kolachi (To be implemented by KPT)	Initial	0		100	0
Total sewerage treatment capacity (MGD)					560	

Source: KWSB, 2019 & KPT, 2020

The study showed that progress in the construction of sewerage treatment plants was very slow. It takes more time to functionalize only two sewerage treatment plants. The treatment capacity of TP-I and TP-III is about 280 MGD, which is 59 percent of the total sewage produced in the city. KWSB and KPT were both unable to even launch TP-IV and TP-V, which shows in case of completion of TP-I and TP-III, more than 41 percent of urban wastewater will continue to be discharged into the sea without treatment. It showed that the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board was unable to fulfill its statutory role in managing the sewage system for the collection, pumping, treatment and disposal of domestic and industrial waste.

8-Conclusion and recommendations

Karachi has serious concern about drainage of untreated waste water, and the count is around 471 million gallons per day (MGD) of municipal wastewater is drained into the sea without getting any treatment. Karachi get more than 12,000 tons of solid waste per day, and about sixty percent of the solid waste is discarded at reserved landfills, and the remaining forty percent remains on the streets and roads of the city. It is observed that heavy discharge of municipal wastewater into the sea without treatment destructs the creation of marine fisheries and deteriorates the state of the coastal areas of Karachi, poses a risk to social health and the extermination of four mangrove forests. Pakistan has a small fishing industry, which makes a significant contribution to the national economy. But due to the strong discharge of toxic water, the fishing industry is being destroyed. Due to degradation of ecosystems, unsustainable exploitation of marine resources, some fish species either disappeared or their production slowed down. The results showed that the average annual growth rate of marine fish catch remained at 0.68 percent during 2000-19 against the 3.55 percent average annual growth rate of in land fish catch, during the same period.

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In addition, municipal wastewater and the remaining remnants of solid waste pass through various drains, nallahs and two major rivers, such as Malir and Lyari, are ultimately discharged into the Arabian Sea without treatment. Pollutants enter rivers and the Arabian Sea directly from urban sewers and industrial waste in the form of hazardous and toxic waters. The mining process released some minerals which are caused as a threat to the life history and development of coral polyps. The beaches of Clifton, Manora, and the Sea wascorrupted, and most of the territories of these tanks lack a favorable environment. The port Qasim is badly affected due discharges by the thermal powers,Steel Mill, tanneries and organic matters from cattle colony. The waste which is discharged into sea by any means gathers on beaches, as well as in shallow coastal waters, which as a result pollutes beaches and poses a danger to human health.

Mangroves in Pakistan are very common in the Indus Delta, which accounts for 97 percent of the total coverage of mangroves; while the remaining 3 percent of the mangroves are located in three places along the coast of Baluchistan. Initially, eight species of mangroves were found in the Indus Delta; however, four of them became extinct because of increased salinity due to untreated urban wastewater. The study concluded that progress in the construction of wastewater treatment plants was very disgusting, and completion of TP-I and TP-III need more time to functionalize. The treatment capacity of TP-I and TP-III together is about 280 MGD, which is 59 percent of the total amount of wastewater produced in the city. KWSB and KPT could not even launch TP-IV and TP-V. It showed that if TP-I and TP-III are completed, more than 41 percent of urban wastewater will continue to be discharged into the sea without treatment. This showed that Karachi Water and Sewerage Board was unable to fulfill its statutory role in managing the sewage system for the collection, pumping, treatment and disposal of domestic and industrial waste.

In order to solve the biggest sewage problem in Karachi, it is recommended that the projects initiated under the Greater Karachi Sewerage Plan be implemented as a priority, and efforts should be made to functionalize all treatment facilities in Karachi. It is necessary to create an independent high-power committee to monitor the future wastewater flow into the Arabian Sea and hold KWSB responsible for not fulfilling the statutory role in managing the sewer system for collecting, pumping, treating, and disposing of household and industrial waste. In addition, government authorities in Karachi have planned to create five sewage treatment plants to handle huge municipal wastewater before it enters the sea, so it is necessary that the wastewater treated at various treatment plants be used for gardening and horticulture in the city.

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